

MODERN HIGHER EDUCATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: DEVELOPMENT TRENDS

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the consideration of the reforms and achieved results in the higher education system in Uzbekistan. In addition, having analyzed the regulatory framework within the issue under consideration, the author highlights the importance of education in achieving the United Nations (UN) sustainable development goals.

Keywords: education, higher education, university, United Nations (UN), sustainable development goals.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada O‘zbekistonda oliy ta’lim tizimida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar, bu borada erishilgan natijalar ko‘rib chiqiladi. Bundan tashqari, ko‘rib chiqilayotgan masala doirasidagi huquqiy bazani tahlil qilib, muallif Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkilotining (BMT) Barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlariga erishishda ta’limning muhimligini ta’kidlaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: ta’lim, oliy ta’lim, universitet, Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti (BMT), barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlari.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена рассмотрению реформ в системе высшего образования Узбекистана, а также достигнутых в этом аспекте результатов. Кроме того, проанализировав нормативно-правовую базу в рамках рассматриваемого вопроса, автор подчеркивает важность образования в достижении целей устойчивого развития Организации Объединенных Наций (ООН).

Ключевые слова: образование, высшее образование, университет, Организация Объединенных Наций (ООН), цели устойчивого развития.

Uzbekistan has been undergoing a significant transformation of the education system. The primary aim of this transformation is to improve the quality of the process of training highly qualified human resources. Current conditions impose new requirements for university graduates in mastering modern knowledge based on advanced cutting-edge information and educational technologies, which are required to improve the quality of life of both each individual and society as a whole.

It should be noted that issues of the higher education system have always been the focus of attention of the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The relevance of the topic under consideration is reflected in the adopted decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, within the framework of the problem considered it is necessary to note the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №PD-27 “On the state program for the implementation of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026 in the “Year of Care for People and Quality Education” dated February 28, 2023, №PD-5847 “On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” dated October 8, 2019, as well as the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the National Program of Education in the Field of Human Rights in the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated February 7, 2023.

In particular, the following priority objectives have been determined: “development of public-private partnerships in the field of higher education, raising the level of enrollment in higher education to more than 50 percent based on organizing the activities of public and non-public

higher educational institutions in the regions, creating a healthy competitive environment in the field; inclusion of at least 10 higher educational institutions of the republic in the first 1000 positions of the list of higher educational institutions in the ranking of internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Higher Education или Academic Ranking of World Universities); implementation of advanced standards of higher education, in particular, a gradual transition from education which curricula are aimed at obtaining theoretical knowledge to an education system aimed at developing practical skills in reliance upon the international experience; raising the essence of higher education to a qualitatively new level, establishing the system for training highly qualified personnel capable of finding their place in the labor market and making a worthy contribution to the stable development of the social sphere and economic sectors; gradual implementation of the “University 3.0” concept, which provides for a close connection between education, science, innovation and activities for the commercialization of research results in higher educational institutions” (Decree, 2019).

In addition, the issues of the higher education development have been investigated in the research papers of a number of scholars and researchers. The majority of scholars highlight the significance and necessity of reforms, which must be implemented in the higher education sphere to raise it to a new level.

Speaking on September 20, 2023 at the 78th session of the United Nations General Assembly, the President of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev has noted the following: “Development of human capital and the education of a creative young generation is one of the strategic objectives that Uzbekistan has set for itself. We are convinced that accessible and quality education for all is the most effective factor in eradicating poverty, improving the well-being of the population and achieving sustainable economic growth. In this regard, our country has accumulated a lot of experience in recent years - a radical transformation of the education system is being carried out. Over the past six years, enrollment in preschool education has increased from 21 percent to 70 percent, and in higher education from 9 percent to 38 percent. The opportunities will be created for every child to attend kindergarten, and every second school graduate to study at a university by 2030. Moreover, we are undertaking systematic activities to achieve gender equality. In particular, 49 percent of students who entered universities last year were girls” (Mirziyoyev, 2023).

Among current trends that fundamentally change the foundations of the world order, the trend of transition to sustainable development is of particular importance. Climate change and mankind’s anthropogenic impact on nature have reached a critical point - their consequences in the form of fires, floods, environmental poisoning have caused the death of a significant number of species of flora and fauna, a decrease in diversity and the emergence of threats to human health and life. A number of experts believe that humanity has entered a new era of its existence - the “Anthropocene”: this is the era of significant human impact on the geology and ecosystem of the Earth.

Education is considered one of the key tools in achieving the United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals. The Sustainable Development Goals are global issues that require the joint efforts of all countries to preserve the planet and ensure the well-being of people.

In Uzbekistan, the issue of education within the framework of this issue began to be considered after the country approved the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in September 2015. This year, the United Nations announced the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which contained 17 interconnected goals as “a plan for achieving a better and more sustainable future for all” (UNDP, 2015).

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev has also mentioned the importance and necessity of adopting a special resolution of the UN General Assembly on raising the role of parliaments in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals and ensuring human rights. Subsequently, the 17 main Sustainable Development Goals of the country until 2023 were approved on October 20, 2018 by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers “On measures to implement the National Goals and Objectives in the field of sustainable development for the period until 2030” (Resolution, 2018).

In 1987, the name of the new concept of Sustainable Development was first used in the meaning of the development in which current activities and meeting the needs of modern society do not harm subsequent generations, but find a mutual balance. Scholars and experts from various countries focus on different features of sustainable development, which is determined both by ideological and scientific foundations, and by a system of national goals. For example, sustainable development can be revealed through potential, which reflects the capabilities required for sustainable development.

Research of the sustainability issues has expanded dramatically since the mid-1980s, and in the early years of this century, the field of sustainability science has emerged as a global network of collaboration. The field as a whole is growing so quickly that any research quickly becomes irrelevant.

Currently along with research and educational activities the universities are increasingly involved in solving social problems of society. They find themselves engaged in solving the social problems of a particular territory, both indirectly through research and training (retraining) of personnel, and directly through a wide range of volunteer, charitable, educational, and socio-cultural activities. In this regard in many cases they play the role of city-forming organizations, finding themselves at the center of the infrastructure that ensures the sustainable development of individual regions and cities, including the solution of social problems.

Universities in modern conditions focus a lot of attention on the implementation of educational programs for the training of highly qualified personnel who remain in demand in the long term, which will enable them to influence the reduction of unemployment. This requires them to not only monitor the regional and national labor markets and trends in the international labor market, but also actively collaborate with both local authorities and business representatives to determine the structure and volume of demand in the labor market, taking into account predicted trends, i.e. formation of specific orders for specialists, implementation of specific targeted recruitments.

The higher education field is currently undergoing fundamental changes in terms of its role in society, principles and methods of work, organization and management. The global leading universities are in search of new models and are actively rethinking their missions.

Currently one of the most recognized models is the approach that determines the trajectory of change in modern university models towards the University 3.0 model, simultaneously implementing three missions: educational, research and innovation, aimed at the commercialization of knowledge. However, in addition to the active transition of many universities to the University 3.0 model, in modern conditions a new promising and future-oriented model of University 4.0 is being developed. Its mission is defined not only as education, science and innovation, but also as the integration of various structures of society to solve problems of sustainable development of the society.

Thus, universities in the US and UK, which are leaders (in the top 5) in the QSWUR 2023 ranking, are highly rated for their contribution to the SDGs. 48 Russian universities were represented in the QSWUR 2023 global ranking.

In this context the relevance of education is that it plays a crucially important role in the implementation of the following UN goals:

Ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education: UN Goal 4 is to ensure access to quality education for all people at all ages. Education is the foundation of human development and self-sufficiency and should be available to everyone, without distinction of age, gender or location.

Improving the level of literacy and skills: Goal 4 also includes improving the literacy and skills of the population. Education should provide opportunities to acquire basic reading, writing and arithmetic skills, as well as develop more complex skills such as critical thinking, creativity and job skills.

Promoting gender equality: UN Goal 5 aims to achieve gender equality, and education is an important factor in this area. Education should provide equal opportunities for boys and girls, and develop awareness of gender issues.

Supporting sustainable educational practices: Education should encourage sustainable development and environmental awareness. This means teaching people to care for the environment, understanding the connections between nature and humans, and promoting sustainable lifestyles.

In conclusion, it should be noted that currently the university is acquiring a central and significant role. This is the new mission of the modern university – a university for society. The possibility of its implementation in each specific university ensures its success and competitiveness. The ability of universities to implement the model of a socially oriented university and operate within its framework determines (determines) the success of the development of a particular region and the country as a whole.

Reference

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